

ON THE INVERSE IDENTIFICATION OF WOOD ELASTIC PROPERTIES USING A DIC-BASED FEMU APPROACH

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Received (Day Month Year)

Revised (Day Month Year)

Accepted (Day Month Year)

Abstract

This work aims to identify the linear elastic orthotropic material parameters of *Pinus pinaster* Ait. wood using full-field measurements and an inverse identification strategy based on the finite element method updating (FEMU) technique. Compression tests are carried out under uniaxial and quasi-static loading conditions on wood specimens oriented on the radial-tangential plane, with different fibre orientations: (i) on-axis and (ii) off-axis specimens with a grain orientation of 60° to the loading direction. Full-field displacements and strains are measured using digital image correlation (DIC), which are then used as a reference in the identification procedure. A finite element model is developed assuming plane stress conditions, where wood is modelled as an orthotropic homogeneous material. Based on the numerical results, a synthetic deformed image is created and processed by DIC and further compared to the experimental results. This approach ensures a fair comparison between both sets of data since the full-field strain maps are obtained through the same filter and therefore have the same strain formulation, spatial resolution and data filtering. Firstly, the identification is performed using a single configuration, either the on-axis or the off-axis specimen. Secondly, the identification is carried out by merging data from both on-axis and off-axis configurations. Moreover, the results obtained from this DIC-based FEMU inverse identification methodology are compared to the ones from the classical FEMU approach. The results from both approaches were similar when using multiple configurations. However, when using the DIC-based FEMU approach with the on-axis configuration, the identified modulus of elasticity in the tangential direction and shear modulus are closer to the reference values, demonstrating its superiority.

Keywords Wood; digital image correlation; inverse identification; orthotropic elasticity; finite element method updating; virtual experiments.

Paper type Research paper

1. Introduction

Engineering materials made from renewable and recyclable natural resources have regained popularity in recent years as a means of achieving sustainable policies and practices toward a green economy (FitzPatrick *et al.*, 2010). Wood is one of the most widely utilised natural materials in the world, with applications ranging from building construction to weaponry, tool manufacture, furniture, music instruments and art (Usta, 2016). Wood is a complex anisotropic and hierarchical biological material with intricate mechanical properties, which proves to be an additional layer of complexity in terms of modelling and experimental characterisation. Wood is commonly described as a linear elastic orthotropic material at low levels of stress (in the elastic regime), short loading periods, and small fluctuations in moisture content and temperature (Xavier *et al.*, 2009). Locally, three orthotropic material directions are established: the longitudinal (L), radial (R), and tangential (T) directions of the wood cells. Clear wood may be analysed as a continuous and homogenous material at the macroscopic scale. There are, however, varying degrees of heterogeneity, such as varying physical and mechanical characteristics at the growth ring scale in earlywood (EW) and latewood (LW) cellular tissues (Dang *et al.*, 2018).

The use of wood and wood-based products in structural applications requires knowledge of the material's behaviour under mechanical loads. In the radial-tangential (RT) plane, a linear elastic orthotropic constitutive model is determined by four material parameters. Classically, these parameters are determined by performing a series of independent homogeneous mechanical tests, from which a simple strain state is assumed in the gauge region. However, due to the restrictive hypotheses (such as uniform strain and stress field at the gauge section, which limits its use to appropriately address the spatial variability of material properties), the classical experimental approach might be inaccurate and time-consuming for the complete material parameter identification (Xavier and Pierron, 2018).

The recent advancements in full-field optical methods, which provide measurements across a whole region of interest (ROI), have enabled innovative material parameter identification procedures (Grédiac and Hild, 2012). Particularly, digital image correlation (DIC) has gained popularity in recent years due to its robustness, while also providing a good balance between spatial resolution and accuracy (Pan *et al.*, 2009; Sutton *et al.*, 2009; Grédiac *et al.*, 2017; Cunha *et al.*, 2021). These rich kinematic field measurements can then be used as input for an inverse identification technique to identify multiple parameters with a single test configuration, given that the test configuration produces sufficiently heterogeneous strain and stress fields so that all material parameters play a role in the mechanical behaviour. This approach has shown to be promising, particularly in heterogeneous materials such as wood, where strain gradients are to be expected due to the annual growth ring structure, and it has already been used by some authors in material parameter identification (Li *et al.*, 2013; Pereira *et al.*, 2018; Henriques *et al.*, 2022).

Several inverse identification techniques have been developed to make use of full-field data, including the equilibrium gap method (EGM) (Claire *et al.*, 2004), the constitutive

equation gap method (CEGM) (Latourte *et al.*, 2008), the finite element model updating method (FEMU) (Kavanagh and Clough, 1971; Kavanagh, 1972; Courtade *et al.*, 1975), and the virtual fields method (VFM) (Grédiac *et al.*, 2006; Pierron and Grédiac, 2012). Among these techniques, the FEMU and the VFM have gradually established themselves as the two major approaches for identifying material parameters when there is no closed-form relationship between these unknowns and the field measurements. A comparison between these inverse identification techniques for the case of homogeneous isotropic linear elasticity and isotropic plasticity with isotropic hardening has been carried out by Martins *et al.* (2018). The authors found that the different approaches had similar performances in elasticity, except for EGM which has a higher sensitivity to noise than the other methods. On the other hand, in elastoplasticity, the FEMU proved to be the most accurate at the expense of increased computational time, while the VFM had quite accurate results while also having the lowest computational time. Nonetheless, the results obtained with VFM could be further enhanced by selecting more advanced virtual fields, such as sensitivity-based virtual fields (Marek *et al.*, 2017), rather than manually defined virtual fields.

The material parameters identification should always be validated with experimental results since this step is essential for establishing credibility and trust in model predictions for engineering design analysis. Classically, either global (resultant applied force) or point data was used for validation (strain gauges). However, this approach does not consider essential information regarding local deformation. The resultant applied force may agree between the model and the experiment, but the model may fail to accurately reflect strain localisation (Lava *et al.*, 2020). The true strength of full-field experimental data lies in quantitative comparisons, which allows the design engineer to assess the accuracy of the finite element analysis (FEA) and minimise uncertainties more accurately. Traditionally, the data from experimental DIC measurements and FEA would be directly compared. However, the discrepancies in FEA and DIC data caused by differences in spatial convergence in locations with strain gradients might be mistakenly associated with model inaccuracies. This can be due to different aspects, such as the different filtering of regions of high strain gradients, differences in data locations and strain formulations, or different spatial cut-off frequencies (Lava *et al.*, 2020). The photomechanical experimental community has recently focused on an alternative approach to make a fair comparison between the full-field DIC maps and FEA results (Lava *et al.*, 2009). This approach includes synthetically deforming an experimental image of the specimen with the speckle pattern using the numerical results, such as displacements and mesh data and further processing them with DIC, with the same settings as the experimental images. This approach ensures that both sets of data have the same filtering, spatial resolution, and strain formulation, thus eliminating differences in full-field map comparisons that aren't due to inaccuracies in the material constitutive model calibration.

In this work, the characterisation of the linear elastic orthotropic parameters of *Pinus pinaster* Ait. is analysed based on uniaxial compression tests under quasi-static conditions on on-axis and off-axis rectangular specimens oriented on the RT plane. Material

parameters such as modulus of elasticity, *Poisson's* ratio, and shear modulus were identified using heterogeneous full-field displacement and strain maps with strain gradients at the wood growth ring structure, which are obtained through DIC. Two inverse identification methodologies were used: (i) directly comparing the experimental data with the FEA results; (ii) using DIC-levelled FEA data in the comparison with the reference experimental results. The last methodology is also called a virtual experiment (VE) methodology. A finite element (FE) model was implemented assuming plane stress conditions and modelling wood as a homogeneous material. The FEMU method was used for the inverse identification process, which entails the minimisation of a cost function that reflects the difference between the experimental and the DIC-levelled FEA data, including the load and strain fields. The identification is either done using a single test in one FEMU run (the on-axis or off-axis specimens), or also using the two specimen configurations in a single FEMU run. Moreover, the parameters identified when using this methodology are compared to the reference values for this wood species.

2. Methodology

Two different FEMU-based approaches were used to determine the linear elastic orthotropic constitutive parameters of *Pinus pinaster*. Figure 1 depicts the parameter identification procedure using FEMU for the direct comparison and VE methodologies. The flowchart is divided into three sections: (i) the experimental tests and the data processing which is used as reference (top), (ii) the iterative process using the direct comparison methodology (left) and (iii) the iterative process using the VE methodology (right). The DIC technique was used to obtain full-field experimental data, which is then compared to numerical results. The DIC settings were chosen using a parametric analysis of several sets of DIC settings. The FE model integrated the DIC-retrieved experimental boundary conditions (BC). The numerical results of the direct comparison approach are iteratively interpolated from the FEA to the DIC data points before being compared to the reference experimental measurements. In contrast, the DIC-levelled FEA results in the VE methodology are iteratively generated by synthetically deforming the reference speckle pattern image using the numerical results, eliminating the need for additional interpolation steps. The reference speckle pattern is the same speckle pattern used experimentally. The material parameter set is iteratively updated using an optimisation method to minimise the differences between experimental and numerical results until convergence is reached. The wood specimens and experimental tests used to characterise the material behaviour, as well as the full-field measurement technique, are described in the following subsections. Furthermore, the FE model, as well as the constitutive model, are outlined. Finally, the FEMU technique is described along with the cost function and optimisation algorithm used.

Fig. 1. Flowchart describing the methodology for the direct comparison approach and the virtual experimental approach with the experimental reference measurements (top), iterative processes of the direct comparison approach (left) and of the virtual experiment methodology (right).

2.1. Material and specimens

Radial boards oriented in the RT material plane were cut from a single *Pinus pinaster* tree of approximately 60 years old at the diameter at breast height. The radial boards were air-dried to a moisture content of around 12%. Wood specimens were then manufactured with nominal dimensions of 20(R)×10(T)×4(L) mm³, for two different configurations: (i) on-axis specimen oriented on the RT plane and (ii) off-axis specimen with an orientation to the grain of about 60°. The off-axis angle was based on a preliminary calculation of anisotropic elasticity theory, aiming at balancing out both linear and shear in-plane strain components in the material coordinate system (Xavier *et al.*, 2007; Xavier *et al.*, 2009). To prevent buckling, the specimens were chosen with a length-to-width ratio of two. The speckle pattern application presented some challenges due to the material's natural porosity and surface roughness. The speckle pattern application procedure started with an initial

layer of white paint applied to the specimen surface to level it. After polishing the first layer, a second layer of white paint was applied before spray painting the speckles. Specimens were stabilised for several hours before testing at a laboratory temperature of about 22 °C and relative humidity of about 60%.

2.2. Experimental tests

Uniaxial compression tests were performed at a controlled cross-head displacement rate of 0.5 mm/min using an Instron 5848 MicroTester machine. To decrease friction and avoid excessive barreling, a lubricant was applied between the specimen and the compression platens. Before testing, the specimen was loaded and unloaded with up to 20 N to improve the flatness of the contact surfaces. A 2 kN load cell was used to measure the axial load, while DIC was used to assess specimen deformation over the entire ROI, which included multiple annual growth rings. The optical system included a Baumer Optronic FWX20 camera (Baumer Optronic GmbH, Radeberg, Germany) with an AF Micro-Nikkor 200mm f/4D ED-IF lens (Nikon, Portugal). The working distance was 742 mm, with a field of vision of 20.5×15.5 mm². Airbrush painting was used to produce the speckle pattern, which has an average speckle size of 3.35 pixels/0.045 mm. The lighting system and exposure time were calibrated to minimise pixel saturation and ensure the best contrast of the speckle pattern. During the test, the loading and image recording were synced at a 1 Hz acquisition frequency. Fig. 2 (adapted from Henriques *et al.*, 2021) illustrates the specimen geometry and experimental boundary conditions for the on-axis specimen (see Fig 2.a) and the off-axis specimen (see Fig 2.b).

Fig. 2. Specimen geometry and experimental boundary conditions regarding: (a) on-axis specimen and (b) off-axis specimen (adapted from Henriques *et al.*, 2021).

2.3. Digital image correlation

The subset-based 2D-DIC technique was used to measure the displacements and strain fields over the ROI of the specimen using the MatchID software (MatchID, 2021). To find the appropriate DIC settings, a performance analysis was conducted using the MatchID's performance analysis module with different sets of settings, by comparing the signal measured for the strain component in the radial direction to the virtual strain gauge (VSG) size on earlywood and latewood points. Because the off-axis angle orientation provides a distinct mechanical response under the same uniaxial compressive load, this investigation

was carried out on both on-axis and off-axis specimens. This choice was made by balancing accuracy and spatial resolution, which results in adequate spatial resolution, which is especially important in complex heterogeneous materials like wood, as well as good accuracy. Table 1 lists the hardware and 2D-DIC parameters used in this work.

2.4. Finite element analysis and constitutive model

The reference experimental test previously specified was modelled using ANSYS Mechanical APDL software (ANSYS, 2021) assuming plane stress conditions using approximately 30000 elements for the on-axis specimen and 25000 for the off-axis specimen. The PLANE182 element was selected, which is a 2D four-node structural solid element. The DIC-retrieved experimental measurements were used as displacement boundary conditions on the left and right boundaries of the specimen on the FE model, which was previously interpolated between DIC and FEA meshes. Wood was modelled as a homogeneous orthotropic material, for one carefully selected time step of the reference experimental test, in order to achieve a good signal-to-noise ratio, while also making sure that the material is still undergoing linear elastic deformation.

Table 1. DIC settings used for the full-field measurements using MatchID software (MatchID, 2021).

DIC settings	
Camera	Baumer Optronic FWX20
Lens	AF Micro-Nikkor 200mm f/4D ED-IF
Field of view	21.5×16.5 mm ²
Image conversion factor	0.0132 mm/px
Working distance	721 mm
Image acquisition frequency	1 Hz
Speckle pattern technique	Airbrush painting
Average speckle size	3.35 px/0.045 mm
Image resolution	1624×1236 px ²
Correlation criterion	ZNSSD
Interpolant	Bicubic spline
Subset shape function	Quadratic
Subset size	17 px (on-axis) 21 px (off-axis)
Step size	5 px
Image pre-filtering	Gaussian, 5 px kernel
Strain window size	9 (on-axis) 11 (off-axis)
Strain interpolation	Bilinear Q4
Strain formulation	Green-Lagrange
Displacement noise-floor	3×10 ⁻² px, 4×10 ⁻¹ μm (on-axis) 3×10 ⁻² px, 4×10 ⁻¹ μm (off-axis)
Strain noise-floor	5×10 ⁻⁴ (on-axis) 3×10 ⁻⁴ (off-axis)

The constitutive model chosen assumes an orthotropic linear elastic behaviour described by the Hooke's law, which for plane stress conditions can be written as (Jones, 1999):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_x \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_y \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{xx} & Q_{xy} & 0 \\ Q_{xy} & Q_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}_i$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_i$ are the in-plane stress and strain components, respectively, and Q_{ij} are the stiffness matrix components. This equation that relates stress and strain can also be expressed regarding the modulus of elasticity and the *Poisson's* ration in the orthotropic material directions (Jones, 1999):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\sigma}_x \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_y \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma}_s \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{E_x}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{-\nu_{xy}E_x}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ \frac{-\nu_{xy}E_y}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & \frac{E_y}{1-\nu_{xy}\nu_{yx}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{xy} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y \\ \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_s \end{bmatrix}, \quad \nu_{yx} = \nu_{xy} \frac{E_y}{E_x}. \quad (2)$$

As presented by equations (1) or (2), the chosen constitutive model is described by four independent material parameters, being the only optimisation variables to calibrate. The reference parameters for the *Pinus pinaster* (Pereira *et al.*, 2018) are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Reference linear elastic orthotropic constitutive parameters of *Pinus pinaster* (Pereira *et al.*, 2018).

	E_R (MPa)	E_T (MPa)	ν_{RT}	G_{RT} (MPa)
Reference parameters	1912	1010	0.586	176

2.5. Finite element model updating technique and synthetic images

The FEMU method was used to determine the material constitutive parameters. An optimization procedure was implemented to iteratively update the unknown material parameters set in order to minimise a cost function that reflects the differences between the experimental DIC measurements and FEA results. Two methodologies were investigated in this work: (i) directly comparing FEA findings to reference measurements, which is the classical FEMU approach and (ii) iteratively creating DIC-levelled FEA results and comparing them to the reference measurements, referred to as the VE methodology (see Fig. 1).

In the VE methodology, the MatchID FE Deformation module (MatchID, 2021) was used to generate synthetic images based on the reference experimental image using the iterative numerical results, including the mesh and displacement fields, which were then analysed using DIC. Afterwards, the MatchID FE Validation module (MatchID, 2021) was used to process the iteratively generated synthetic images with DIC, using the same DIC settings and ROI as in the experimental analysis. This approach guarantees a fair comparison between the numerical and experimental results, ensuring consistency in data filtering, spatial resolution, and strain formulation across both data sets. Additionally,

because this method uses an actual image of a speckle pattern, the experimental error sources were also incorporated into the DIC-levelled FEA data. Furthermore, this approach did not require additional interpolation steps between the data points of the two data sets, unlike the classical FEMU approach that requires the data interpolation between the DIC and FEA mesh.

To investigate the impact of using multiple tests with different mechanical responses and strain fields on the identification results, both approaches were used in an identification run that uses a single test configuration for both the on-axis and off-axis specimens, as well as a single identification run that uses both specimen configurations. The following cost function was used:

$$\varphi(\boldsymbol{\chi}) = (1 - W_F)IT_S^2(\boldsymbol{\chi}) + W_FIT_F^2(\boldsymbol{\chi}), \quad (3)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\chi}$ is the vector of the unknown set of material parameters ($E_R, E_T, \nu_{RT}, G_{RT}$), W_F is a weighting coefficient between the strain (IT_S) and force (IT_F) terms. The strain term can be written as:

$$IT_S(\boldsymbol{\chi}) = \frac{1}{3n_p n_t} \sum_{i=1}^{n_t} \left[\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{n_p} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{xx}^{\text{exp}} - \varepsilon_{xx}^{\text{num}}(\boldsymbol{\chi})}{\varepsilon_{xx, \text{max}}^{\text{exp}}} \right)_j^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{n_p} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{yy}^{\text{exp}} - \varepsilon_{yy}^{\text{num}}(\boldsymbol{\chi})}{\varepsilon_{yy, \text{max}}^{\text{exp}}} \right)_j^2} + \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^{n_p} \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{xy}^{\text{exp}} - \varepsilon_{xy}^{\text{num}}(\boldsymbol{\chi})}{\varepsilon_{xy, \text{max}}^{\text{exp}}} \right)_j^2} \right], \quad (4)$$

where n_p and n_t are the total number of measurement points and experimental test configuration, respectively, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the in-plane strain tensor. The superscripts “exp” and “num” refer to the experimental measurements and the numerical results, respectively, whereas the subscript “max” refers to the maximum strain value of each in-plane component for each test. Similarly, the force term is characterised as follows:

$$IT_F(\boldsymbol{\chi}) = \frac{1}{n_t} \sum_{j=1}^{n_t} \left| \frac{F^{\text{exp}} - F^{\text{num}}}{F^{\text{exp}}} \right|_j, \quad (5)$$

where F^{exp} and F^{num} describe the experimental and numerical loads, respectively. Moreover, the W_F used in this experimental identification is 10^{-1} , which privileges the strain term minimisation, while also being capable of minimising the difference between the numerical and experimental loads, as was studied previously in the work produced by Henriques *et al.* (2021). Using the Matlab Optimization toolbox (The MathWorks, Inc., 2021), the Nelder-Mead simplex method, which is a direct search algorithm, was used.

3. Results

3.1. Classical FEMU: the direct comparison approach

The classical FEMU technique with the direct comparison between DIC and FE was used and the optimised solutions for the material parameters were achieved. The initial parameter set used was the reference values (see Table 2). Three distinct identification runs were carried out, the first with the on-axis specimen, the second with the off-axis specimen, and the third with both specimen configurations combined in a single identification run. Table 3 shows the results for each of the identification runs, the initial parameters set (reference values), the lower and upper boundaries, the cost function value along with each of its terms (IT_S and IT_F) and the computational time required when using a computer, with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8700K (3.70 GHz) processor and 16.0 GB of RAM memory. The results show that the modulus of elasticity in the radial direction is more sensitive to the on-axis specimen configuration, whereas the shear modulus appears to be more sensitive to the off-axis specimen configuration, as expected. The results also show an improvement when using both specimen configurations in a single identification run, with the cost function value and strain term value being reduced. Although the force term value in the double specimen configuration run is slightly higher, it is still low and equals a load difference of less than 0.1 N.

Table 3. Reference (Pereira *et al.*, 2018), initial and calibrated parameters set, lower and upper boundaries, computational time required and cost function value and its terms for the different identification runs using the classical FEMU technique.

	E_R (MPa)	E_T (MPa)	ν_{RT}	G_{RT} (MPa)	$\varphi(\chi)$	IT_S	IT_F
Reference	1912	1010	0.586	176	-	-	-
Lower boundary	1	1	0.01	1	-	-	-
Upper boundary	10^5	10^5	2	10^5	-	-	-
On-axis specimen – CPU time: 170 minutes (1.00 relative time)							
Initial set	1912	1010	0.586	176	2.234×10^{-3}	1.122×10^{-2}	1.456×10^{-1}
Id. parameters	1706	2414	0.726	997	9.569×10^{-5}	1.031×10^{-2}	2.058×10^{-8}
Off-axis specimen – CPU time: 176 minutes (1.04 relative time)							
Initial set	1912	1010	0.586	176	4.538×10^{-3}	7.732×10^{-3}	2.117×10^{-1}
Id. parameters	526	418	0.670	163	3.648×10^{-5}	6.366×10^{-3}	5.852×10^{-8}
On axis + off-axis specimens – CPU time: 312 minutes (1.84 relative time)							
Initial set	1912	1010	0.586	176	3.214×10^{-3}	4.805×10^{-3}	1.787×10^{-1}
Id. parameters	1663	518	0.722	165	1.774×10^{-5}	4.440×10^{-3}	1.956×10^{-5}

Fig. 3 depicts the convergence of each material parameter, the cost function, and the strain and force terms of the cost function throughout the optimisation procedure for each of the identification runs. The greater sensitivity of the modulus of elasticity in the radial direction to the on-axis specimen configuration is also noticeable in Fig. 3.a, where the runs with the on-axis specimen configurations converge significantly faster and closer to the reference value. Moreover, the shear modulus is seen to be more sensitive to the off-axis specimen configuration in Fig. 3.d, convergent to values that are closer to reference.

Fig. 3. Convergence study of the identified parameters, cost function and cost function terms values for the classical FEMU approach: (a) E_R , (b) E_T , (c) ν_{RT} , (d) G_{RT} , (e) cost function value and (f) strain and force terms values.

Furthermore, the cost function value is lower for the run with the two specimen configurations due to the reduction in strain field differences, as indicated by the strain term in Fig. 3.f.

Figure 4 depicts the experimental DIC strain fields and the calibrated numerical strain fields for all of the previous identification runs described using the traditional FEMU approach, as well as the differences between both strain maps normalised by the maximum value of each in-plane strain component. Furthermore, the FE model was developed considering a homogeneous material, whereas the annual growth rings structure generates a heterogeneous strain map as a result of stiffness variations between the wood meso layers, as reflected in the differences maps, which exhibit a periodic pattern, particularly in the early wood layer, where the strain components are underestimated.

3.2. DIC-based FEMU: the virtual experiment approach

Here, a DIC-based FEMU approach is used, involving iteratively deforming the reference speckle pattern image based on FEA results and then processed by DIC to ensure a fair comparison between the two data sets. Similarly, the initial parameters are the reference values, and the lower and upper boundaries are the same as those previously presented. Three identification runs for the previously described specimen configurations were performed, with the results, initial parameters set, lower and upper boundaries, cost function value and of its terms, and computational time required presented in Table 4. The identification results obtained using the DIC-based approach are comparable to those obtained using the traditional FEMU approach, including the cost function and its terms. Nevertheless, it is possible to notice that the identified modulus of elasticity in the tangential direction and the shear modulus are closer to the reference values.

Furthermore, the results obtained in both methodologies when using the two specimen configurations in a single identification run are consistent. Also, the results differ from the reference values typically reported in the literature. The convergence of each material parameter, the cost function, and the strain and force components of the cost function during the optimisation process for each of the identification runs is shown in Fig. 5. Similarly to the direct comparison approach, the cost function value for the identification run with the two specimen configurations is lower due to the reduction in strain field differences. Furthermore, the sensitivity of the identified parameters exhibit similar behaviour to the traditional FEMU approach, with the modulus of elasticity in the radial direction being more sensitive to the on-axis specimen configuration and the shear modulus being more sensitive to the off-axis specimen configuration. This is to be expected given that both methodologies used the same experimental data, and the sensitivity of a given constitutive parameter is related to the material's mechanical response and thus highly dependent on the experimental test configuration used.

The experimental DIC strain fields, the VE strain fields and the normalized difference between both fields are presented in Fig. 6. Similarly to the traditional FEMU identification results, the residual differences between both fields show the annual growth ring pattern due to the homogeneous modelling of the material used in this work.

Fig. 4. Full-field strain measurements, numerical results and differences between both strain maps for each of the in-plane strain component for the following identification runs with the traditional FEMU: (a) on-axis specimen (stage at load 298.8 N and numerical load at 298.8 N), (b) off-axis specimen (stage at load 106.0 N and numerical load at 298.8 N) and (c) On-axis specimen (stage at load 298.8 N and numerical load at 298.8 N) and off-axis specimen (stage at load 106.0 N and numerical load at 106.0 N).

The residual differences maps for the in-plane components are similar to the maps obtained with traditional FEMU, which is supported by the similar value of the strain term component indicated in tables 3 and 4. The biggest difference in the strain maps for both methods is the use of two specimen configurations simultaneously rather than a single configuration, which is also indicated by a decrease in the strain term value when using both specimen configurations in the identification process.

Table 4. Reference (Pereira *et al.*, 2018), initial and calibrated parameters set, lower and upper boundaries, computational time required and cost function value and its terms for the different identification runs using the DIC-based FEMU technique.

	E_R (MPa)	E_T (MPa)	ν_{RT}	G_{RT} (MPa)	$\varphi(\chi)$	IT_S	IT_F
Reference	1912	1010	0.586	176	-	-	-
Lower boundary	1	1	0.01	1	-	-	-
Upper boundary	10^5	10^5	2	10^5	-	-	-
On-axis specimen – CPU time: 394 minutes (2.32 relative time)							
Initial set	1912	1010	0.586	176	2.234×10^{-3}	1.120×10^{-2}	1.456×10^{-1}
Id. parameters	1687	1250	0.698	623	9.682×10^{-5}	1.037×10^{-2}	2.198×10^{-8}
Off-axis specimen – CPU time: 608 minutes (3.58 relative time)							
Initial set	1912	1010	0.586	176	4.539×10^{-3}	7.821×10^{-3}	2.117×10^{-1}
Id. parameters	521	418	0.679	162	3.718×10^{-5}	6.427×10^{-3}	9.683×10^{-6}
On axis + off-axis specimens – CPU time: 1250 minutes (7.36 relative time)							
Initial set	1912	1010	0.586	176	3.214×10^{-3}	4.824×10^{-3}	1.787×10^{-1}
Id. parameters	1663	518	0.718	165	1.789×10^{-5}	4.459×10^{-3}	2.121×10^{-5}

4. Discussion

When using on-axis and off-axis specimen configurations, both traditional and DIC-based FEMU approaches appear to produce comparable results. When the single test configurations are used, however, there are differences, particularly in the case of the on-axis specimen, where the DIC-based approach has identified a modulus of elasticity in the tangential direction and a shear modulus that are closer to the reference values for this wood species. These two parameters are less sensitive to the on-axis specimen configuration, while the modulus of elasticity in the radial direction is less sensitive to the off-axis specimen configuration. This suggests that there is a dependency of the identifiability of material parameters on the test configuration used due to the lack of sufficiently heterogeneous strain fields. However, when these two specimen configurations are combined in a single identification run, the identification results are close to the reference values, with some differences expected due to wood's natural variability. It would

be necessary to conduct a statistical analysis on the identification results of a larger number of specimens to account for this natural variability, which has already been done in previous studies (Henriques *et al.*, 2022). The DIC-based FEMU approach is expected to better reproduce the experimental strain fields, due to processing the numerical results with the same data filtering as the experimental results. However, both approaches have similar calibrated cost functions and strain term values. This could be because the numerical model was not able to better reproduce the experimental strain fields due to the homogeneous modelling of wood used in this study, which is naturally a heterogeneous material.

Fig. 5. Convergence study of the identified parameters, cost function and cost function terms values for the DIC-based FEMU approach: (a) E_R , (b) E_T , (c) ν_{RT} , (d) G_{RT} , (e) cost function value and (f) strain and force terms values.

Fig. 6. Full-field strain measurements, numerical results and differences between both strain maps for each of the in-plane strain component for the following identification runs with the DIC-based FEMU: (a) on-axis specimen (stage at load 298.8 N and numerical load at 298.8 N), (b) off-axis specimen (stage at load 106.0 N and numerical load at 106.0 N) and (c) On-axis specimen (stage at load 298.8 N and numerical load at 298.8 N) and off-axis specimen (stage at load 106.0 N and numerical load at 106.0 N).

5. Conclusions

Linear elastic orthotropic parameters of *Pinus Pinaster* were determined using DIC and two different inverse identification approaches: (a) the classical FEMU technique, which compares the DIC and FEA results directly, and (b) the DIC-levelled FEA data in comparison with the experimental DIC measurements. Three different identification runs were carried out using: (i) on-axis specimen, (ii) off-axis specimen, and (iii) both specimen configurations simultaneously. The main conclusions that can be drawn from this work are as follows:

- Both methodologies proved to retrieve similar results when both specimen configurations were used in a single run and on the off-axis specimen configuration. However, in the case of the on-axis specimen configuration, the identified modulus of elasticity in the tangential direction and the shear modulus are closer to the reference values for this wood species.
- The calibrated cost function value and its terms are similar for both approaches. This could be due to the homogeneous modelling of wood used in this study, which is a naturally heterogeneous material due to its annual growth ring structure, limiting the numerical model's ability to better reproduce the experimental strain fields measured.
- The results show that the modulus of elasticity in the radial direction is more sensitive to the on-axis specimen configuration, whereas the shear modulus appears to be more sensitive to the off-axis specimen configuration. Furthermore, when both specimen configurations are used in a single identification run, the results appear to be closer to the reference, and the cost function and strain field differences are also smaller, which implies that there is a dependency on the identifiability of certain parameters and the test configuration used.
- The calibrated parameters differ from the reference values typically reported in the literature, even when using both specimen configurations, however, this is expected due to the inherent variability of a natural material such as wood. To account for this natural variability, a statistical study of the identification results of a greater number of specimens would be required.
- In future work, other heterogeneous test configurations could be used in the identification, allowing all material parameters to be identified with a single test configuration. Furthermore, a statistical analysis can be used to determine the mean value of the identified parameters, allowing for the natural variability of wood to be accounted for. Finally, wood could be modelled as a heterogeneous material to improve the numerical model's ability to reproduce experimental strain fields.

Acknowledgments

J. Henriques is grateful to the FCT for the PhD grant 2021.05692.BD. This project has received funding from the Research Fund for Coal and Steel under grant agreement No 888153. The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial support of the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) under the project PTDC/EMEAPL/29713/2017 by UE/FEDER through the programs CENTRO 2020 and COMPETE 2020, and UID/EMS/00481/2013-FCT under CENTRO-01-0145-FEDER-022083. Authors also acknowledge Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT - MCTES) for its financial support via the projects UIDB/00667/2020 (UNIDEMI).

Disclaimer

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